

Exploring the Patterns of Gender Discrimination in Management Positions in Nigeria's Organizations

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Abstract

This article examines patterns of gender discrimination in management positions in Nigeria's organizations. The article sheds light on the multifaceted nature of gender discrimination in management positions and the various ways in which socioeconomic status can influence this issue underscores the need for a nuanced understanding of socioeconomic status in promoting gender equality initiatives within organizations. Furthermore, the study highlights the significant influence of cultural norms on gender discrimination, which emphasizes the importance of addressing ingrained cultural attitudes and beliefs to create more inclusive workplaces. This suggests that well-designed and effectively implemented policies can play a crucial role in mitigating gender disparities. The study suggests that there is need to give all genders equal opportunities and chance in management positions in organizations regardless of socioeconomic status and cultural background.

Keywords: Corporate world, Gender discrimination, Management positions, Organizations, Wage gap.

1. Introduction

Gender discrimination in management positions is a pervasive issue that has far-reaching consequences in both the corporate world and society at large. This study aims to shed light on the phenomenon, its underlying causes, and the problems it creates. Gender discrimination in management positions refers to the unequal treatment, opportunities, and representation of individuals in leadership roles based on their gender (Folkman and Zenger, 2019). While significant progress has been made in recent decades, this issue remains a major challenge in workplaces across the globe, negatively impacting both women and men (Triventi, 2013).

One of the most significant problems associated with gender discrimination in management positions is the unequal opportunities it creates for men and women. Women are often underrepresented in leadership roles, which limits their access to decision-making processes, career advancement, and overall professional growth. This unequal distribution of opportunities perpetuates the glass ceiling, making it difficult for women to break through and achieve top management positions (Institute of Women and Equal Opportunities, 2016).

Gender discrimination in management positions contributes to the gender wage gap. Women in leadership roles typically earn less than their male counterparts, even when they hold the same or similar positions with equal qualifications and experience. This wage gap is not only

unfair but also contributes to economic disparities between men and women. According to several international sources, women's wages are still significantly lower than men's. Every year, this information is measured by the Gender Equality Index as a tool for measuring the progress of gender equality. It was developed by the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) (2010). EIGE discusses that there are many issues behind the gender gap, such as employment rates, part-time work, unpaid care and parental responsibilities. The index has six main areas - work, money, knowledge, time, power and health - and two secondary areas: violence against women and overlapping inequalities (Delaneuville and Mitková, 2018).

When women are discriminated against in management positions, it results in the underutilization of talent. Organizations miss out on the diverse perspectives and skills that women can bring to the table. This underrepresentation limits the potential for innovation and the ability to address complex business challenges effectively. Women make up a significant portion of key candidate pools. With a value proposition that promotes gender diversity, organizations are more likely to attract talented people that are sensible to the problem and take into consideration gender equality policies when considering different employees. Thus, gender diversity provides an organization with a wider access to a pool of talents in the market (Australian Institute of Management, 2012; Curtis, Schmid and Struber, 2012).

Gender discrimination in management positions can foster a negative organizational culture. When employees witness unequal treatment, it erodes trust in the company's commitment to diversity and inclusion. This can lead to decreased employee morale, job dissatisfaction, and increased turnover, all of which can have significant financial implications for the organization. Gender diversity is strongly correlated with the corporate culture, besides affirmative policies and actions; managing gender diversity requires a shift in corporate culture in order to make the workplace more conducive to the needs of working women (Mckinsey, 2015).

Discrimination in management positions can hinder the professional growth of women, leading to stagnation in their careers. Women may experience limited access to training, mentorship, and networking opportunities, which are essential for career development. This limitation on growth not only affects the individual but also impedes the potential for women to serve as role models and mentors for others. Bridging gender gaps in the workplace is a crucial component of inclusive and sustainable growth. (Seung and Byung, 2020).

Gender discrimination in management positions perpetuates harmful gender stereotypes. It reinforces the notion that certain roles and qualities are inherently masculine or feminine, limiting the freedom of individuals to express their true selves and pursue careers that align with their passions and skills rather than societal expectations.

Despite the extensive research and efforts made to address gender discrimination in management positions, several critical gaps in the literature persist. The majority of studies have predominantly focused on the experiences of white, middle-class women. There is a pressing need for research that explores the intersectionality of gender discrimination, considering how factors such as race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, and disability interact to

create unique challenges for different groups. Much of the existing literature is based on studies conducted in Western contexts. There is a need for a more African and Nigerian perspectives to understand how gender discrimination manifests in different organizations using in Nigeria, which necessitated the present article.

2. Women Participation in Management Positions

Despite the fact that more women than ever before hold managerial positions in corporations, Hoobler, Lemmon, and Wayne (2011) note that many people still find it strange and troublesome when women hold management positions. This researcher offered arguments for why the underrepresentation of women in management roles might indicate to lower-level women that obtaining management jobs is not certain. There are only two reasons for this: one, their poor educational attainment inevitably prevents them from achieving such leadership positions; second, they are not exposed to or mentored by the few women who are now in management roles as a succession strategy. This is partially the reason why some businesses lose the proper people, which can result in low organisational productivity. According to Grant Thorn International Business Reports (2012), women make up one in every two people, and the literature currently in publication indicates that they occupy little more than one in every five senior management positions. According to the report, having and raising children is typically viewed as a hurdle; as a result, imbalances in the boardroom, for instance, might be detrimental to business organisations' prospects for success.

According to Kochanowski (2010), there aren't many women in senior management roles or management at all in the workplace. He stressed that there is still a dearth of women in executive roles and on corporate boards of directors, even in spite of reports on the advancement of women in American workplaces, where they occupy roughly forty (40%) percent of management positions (Kochanowski, 2010, Eagly & Carly, 2007). According to Adler (2001), having more women on boards of directors and in senior positions would benefit companies and have a positive impact. Due to evidence that issues with gender discrimination have an impact on women's involvement in management roles, the gender gap in management positions has often been a subject of discussion.

3. Factors Influencing Gender Discrimination against Women Participation in Management Positions

According to Lomazzi (2020), mentoring might be used as a tactic to increase women's participation in management by helping them believe in themselves and gain confidence in pitching their potential, which would ultimately help them feel acknowledged and valued. In particular, according to Lomazzi (2020), a variety of factors influence the position that women acquire in managerial roles. Among these are the persistence of a group of women who are formally qualified, the psychological and sociocultural obstacles that keep women from achieving top or management positions, and the attitudes that exist inside corporate organisations. According to Geha & Karam (2021), "the main deterrent for the women in organisations is the lack of policy and practise that encourages women to aspire for management positions." Geha and Karam's (2021) research also revealed that women faced experiences and pressures that males did not share. Strain, sadness, loneliness, stereotypes,

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and the overall sense of pressure from institutional and cultural norms that do not support women are some of these pressures. Therefore, it is believed that Kamau's proposal is crucial to understanding some of the elements that contribute to gender discrimination against women's involvement in management positions. The research does, however, highlight the problems that affect women's involvement in management or leadership roles and the need to identify both the areas where prejudice against women may be improving and those where it still exists.

Gender discrimination against women's involvement in management positions is impeded by stereotypes and biases that arise from women's conflicting roles in their advancement towards parity with men in important positions or managerial responsibilities. These are opinions about the characteristics and traits that people are assigned based on their gender (Kleven and Landais, 2017). It is a common occurrence that males and females are stereotyped as having more aggressive, confident, and dominant features, involving being overly ambitious, self-confident, and independent with leadership roles, and that females are more communal and concerned with the welfare of the people, including attributes like kindness, sentiment, generosity, and compassion (Silva and Klasen, 2021). It makes sense, so Abbott (2017) emphasises that there are global variables that contribute to gender discrimination against women holding management roles, and that the gender gap is increasingly obvious at higher organisational levels. Consequently, it is evident that the biggest barrier to women achieving managerial positions in global corporations is the enduring belief that males belong in high positions.

4. Current Status of Women in Decision Making in Corporate Organizations

There are several critiques on the current status of women in management, as well as participating in the decision-making process. Such academic research is beginning to attract the attention of research in developing countries like Nigeria and this is one of the reasons why this study intends to add to existing literatures. One notable issue is influencing the current status of women that debar them from participation decision making is the role of family and its relative impact on women's competing demands and the continued pressure on women to perform dual roles, as individuals in work organizations and as mothers (Hoobler, Lemmon and Wayne, 2011). These acts of mixed roles and the consequential influence on decision making are still very common in developing countries like Nigeria with which government policies in this part of the world are struggling to deal with gender issues, especially at the work place (Matanmi, 2007).

5. Gender Disparities in Leadership Roles

Numerous studies constantly emphasise the notable gender gaps prevalent in leadership and management roles across diverse sectors and geographical areas. The underrepresentation of women in higher-level management positions is a clear manifestation of systematic gender discrimination and prejudices (Eagly & Carli, 2007). There exist a multitude of obstacles that impede the advancement of women into positions of leadership. The factors contributing to the limited progress of women in professional settings encompass stereotypes, limited access to mentoring programmes, unconscious biases, familial obligations, and unfavourable workplace environments (Catalyst, 2019; Eagly & Carli, 2007).

The perpetuation of gender discrimination is significantly influenced by the organisational culture. Certain cultures may consciously or unconsciously endorse gender prejudices, which can have an impact on the decision-making procedures for promotions, assignments, and prospects for professional advancement (Kossek, 2014).

Gender discrimination has a significant impact on both individuals and organisations. The absence of diversity and inclusion within leadership positions has been found to have several negative consequences for organisations. These include a decline in creativity, a restricted range of viewpoints in the decision-making process, diminished employee happiness, and the possibility for legal complications (Kulik, 2014).

The literature study highlights the significant concern of gender discrimination in managerial roles, which is a widespread issue on a global scale. The importance of addressing this matter cannot be overstated as it plays a pivotal role in fostering diversity and inclusion, enhancing organisational efficacy, and guaranteeing equitable prospects for professional advancement.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the study sheds light on the multifaceted nature of gender discrimination in management positions and the various ways in which socioeconomic status can influence this issue. This underscores the need for a nuanced understanding of socioeconomic status in promoting gender equality initiatives within organizations. Furthermore, the study highlights the significant influence of cultural norms on gender discrimination, which emphasizes the importance of addressing ingrained cultural attitudes and beliefs to create more inclusive workplaces. This suggests that well-designed and effectively implemented policies can play a crucial role in mitigating gender disparities. The study suggests that there is need to give all genders equal opportunities and chance in management positions in organizations regardless of socioeconomic status and cultural background.

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